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Page: 6831 (abstract only)
Publication year: 2015
ISBN: 978-84-606-8243-1
ISSN: 2340-1117

Conference name: 7th
International Conference on
Education and New Learning
Technologies
Dates: 6-8 July, 2015
Location: Barcelona, Spain

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CHARACTERIZATION OF SCHOOL SEMIPRESENTIAL UNDERGRADUATE AND GRADUATE SUBJECTS IN THE AREA OF HEALTH PROMOTION AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BRASILIA - UNB

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The sociodemographic characteristics of students in a distance education course are diverse, which consequently can influence the teaching-learning process of this modality. This study proposal is to describe the sociodemographic characteristics of undergraduate and graduate semi-presence disciplines in the area of health promotion and its study habits. 148 students participated in the study. There was a predominance of women, of students who live with their families and with family income above eight minimum wages, with no difference among the groups. But there was a difference between the groups in age, working, being married, living alone and having children. The preponderance of economic, social, demographic and school characteristics may have facilitated the teaching-learning process established in the subjects. However, these characteristics might help developing mediation strategies between the tutor teacher and students, seeking a more active and reflective participation of students.

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keywords: [distance education](#), [semi-presence](#), [educational assessment](#), [higher education](#).